

GREAT BRITISH VALUES AND ITS NATIONAL FOOD

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Abstract.

This is not suitable for the holidays at all, because on the festive table sweets, complex and wonderful dishes look good. British food, on the other hand, is hearty and delicious, but what else is needed for a good holiday.

Keywords: Values, citizen, modern Britain, history, customs, holidays, tradition, law, liberty, respect, religious, regional specialities.

British Values in education refers to a government initiative introduced to teach children the values of democracy, the rule of law, individual liberty, and mutual respect and tolerance, each of which is considered a fundamental British Value. The Department for Education published guidance on implementing British Values in schools in November 2014, to create and enforce a clear and rigorous expectation of all schools to promote them. According to the guidance, promoting British Values means “challenging opinions or behaviours in school that are contrary to fundamental British Values”. It’s outlined that British Values should be upheld as part of pupils’ spiritual, moral, social and cultural development in order to ensure that they leave school prepared for a life in modern Britain. The values underpin what it is to be a citizen in a modern and diverse Britain, and promote moral and cultural understanding, to celebrate the diversity of the UK. Fundamental British Values underpin what it is to be a citizen in a modern and diverse Great Britain valuing our community and celebrating diversity of the UK.

The Government set out its definition of British values in the 2011 Prevent Strategy, and these values have been reiterated this year (2014). At Southfields primary these values are reinforced regularly and are evidenced in the following ways: Schools, through their curriculum, are legally bound to actively promote fundamental British values. Southfields for many years has taught English Heritage and pupils already have developed a good understanding of the country, its history and some of customs, values, democracy, law, liberty, respect and tolerance to actively promote the government are asking all schools to focus on, and show how, the school’s work is effective in securing these British Values as a school we approach this using many different strategies some examples are listed below. As a school we have pupil leadership through the School Council, Interfaith Council, Sports and Arts Ambassador’s, Cares welfare team, Playground Pals, Charity Leader as well as a school

magazine, Community Cadets, Pupil Panel and House Captains. All of these groups lead work within the school to further promote British Values and English Heritage.

As part of our curriculum we also enhance British Values through assemblies and special performances and gatherings such as Mother's Day, Father's Day, May Day dance festival, Country Dancing festival, WW1 and WW2 commemorative days and Poppy Day, Animals in the war day linked with the local donkey sanctuary as well as Christmas Performance, visits from Santa and the Easter Bunny and Church events such as Christingle, Easter service and our own school internal café resource area to promote British traditions, artifacts, food and history which is also adapted half termly to become other countries and cultures.

Democracy

Provide pupils with a broad general knowledge of, and promote respect for, public institutions and services Teach pupils how they can influence decision-making through the democratic process Include in the curriculum information on the advantages and disadvantages of democracy and how it works in Britain. Encourage pupils to become involved in decision-making processes and ensure they are listened to in school Organise visits to the local council and Parliament Hold 'mock elections' so pupils learn how to argue and defend points of view Help pupils to express their views. Teach pupils how public services operate and how they are held to account Model how perceived in justice can be peacefully challenged

Rule of law

Ensure school rules, codes of conduct and expectations are explicit, clear and fair. Help pupils to distinguish right from wrong this is enhanced by our wonderful links with the Police and local PCSOs who fully support the work of the school

Help pupils to respect the law and the basis on which it is made help pupils to understand that living under the rule of law protects individuals. Include visits from the police in the curriculum. Teach pupils aspects of both civil and criminal law and discuss how this might differ from some religious laws. Develop an understanding of restorative justice approaches to resolve conflicts. Restorative justice is a theory of justice that emphasises repairing the harm caused or revealed by criminal behaviour against another person or other people.

According to the laws of Britain and British culture, we keep in touch with their national food which are centuries people use, cook and have with family members and friends. British Culture, British Customs and British Traditions-it has many different manufactures in the field of using tradition and keep them, follow them. Then we are going to open the secrets of traditional; British cuisine, British food, some history, regional specialities, puddings etc, breakfast, bangers and mash, bubble and squeak, fish and chips, Sunday roast, steak, cheese,

sandwiches, Indian food..... Traditional British cuisine is substantial, yet simple and wholesome. They have long believed in four meals a day. Their fare has been influenced by the traditions and tastes from different parts of the British empire: teas from Ceylon and chutney, kedgeree, and mulligatawny soup from India. During Victorian times good old British stodge mixed with exotic spices from all over the Empire. And today despite being part of Europe we've kept up our links with the countries of the former British Empire, now united under the Commonwealth.

Among English cakes and pastries, many are tied to the various religious holidays of the year. Hot Cross Buns are eaten on Good Friday, Simnel Cake is for Mothering Sunday, Plum Pudding for Christmas, and Twelfth Night Cake for Epiphany. The British tradition of stews, pies and breads, according to the taste buds of the rest of the world, went into terminal decline. What was best in England was only that which showed the influence of France, and so English food let itself Although some traditional dishes such as roast beef and Yorkshire pudding, Cornish pasties, steak and kidney pie, bread and butter pudding, treacle tart, spotted dick or fish and chips, remain popular, there has been a significant shift in eating habits in Britain. Rice and pasta have accounted for the decrease in potato consumption and the consumption of meat has also fallen. Vegetable and salad oils have largely replaced the use of butter, come a gastronomic joke and the French art of Nouvell Cuisine was adopted.

Roast beef is still the national culinary pride. It is called a "joint," and is served at midday on Sunday with roasted potatoes, Yorkshire pudding, two vegetables, a good strong horseradish, gravy, and mustard. Today there is more emphasis on fine, fresh ingredients in the better restaurants and markets in the UK offer food items from all over the world. Salmon, Dover sole, exotic fruit, Norwegian prawns and New Zealand lamb are choice items. Wild fowl and game are other specialties on offer. In fact fish is still important to the English diet, we are after all an island surrounded by some of the richest fishing areas of the world. Many species swim in the cold offshore waters: sole, haddock, hake, plaice, cod (the most popular choice for fish and chips), turbot, halibut, mullet and John Dory. Oily fishes also abound (mackerel, pilchards, and herring) as do crustaceans like lobster and oysters. Eel, also common, is cooked into a wonderful pie with lemon, parsley, and shallots, all topped with puff pastry.

REGIONAL SPECIALITIES;

Beefsteak, Oyster, and Kidney Pudding: Black Pudding: invented in Stornoway, Cock-a-Leekie : Crown Roast Lamb: The crown roast encircles a stuffing of apples, bread crumbs, onion, celery, and lemon. Eccles Cake : Puff pastry stuffed with a spicy currant filling. Hasty Pudding: A simple and quick (thus the name) steamed pudding of milk, flour, butter, eggs, and cinnamon.

Irish Stew: An Irish stew always has a common base of lamb, potatoes, and onion. It could contain any number of other ingredients, depending on the cook. Likky Pie Leeks: pork, and cream baked in puff pastry.[4] THE SUNDAY ROAST ; Every Sunday thousands of British families sit down together to eat a veritable feast of roasted meat served with roast potatoes, vegetables and other [accompaniments](#). It is a tradition with a long pedigree, so read on...

How it all began

In medieval times the village serfs served the squire for six days a week. Sundays however were a day of rest, and after the morning church service, serfs would assemble in a field and practice their battle techniques.

They were rewarded with mugs of ale and a feast of oxen roasted on a spit.

Nowadays the tradition has survived because the meat can be put in the oven to roast before the family goes to church and be ready to eat when they return.

Typical meats for roasting are joints of beef, pork, lamb or a whole chicken. More rarely duck, goose, gammon, turkey or game are eaten. The more popular roasts are often served with traditional accompaniments, these are:

roast beef - served with Yorkshire pudding; and horseradish sauce or English mustard as relishes;

roast pork - served with crackling (the crispy skin of the pork) and sage and onion **stuffing**; apple sauce and English mustard as relishes
roast lamb - served with sage and onion stuffing and mint sauce as a relish
roast chicken - served with pigs in blankets, chipolata sausages and stuffing, and bread sauce or cranberry sauce or redcurrant jelly

Any self respecting Sunday roast should be served with a gravy made from the meat juices.

References:

1. Another interesting site can be found at [//www.nutrition.org.uk/](http://www.nutrition.org.uk/) including a great information section.
2. British Culture, British Customs and British Traditions "BRITISH FOOD" (Copyright The Learn English Network - All Rights Reserved These pages are best viewed using the latest version of Chrome, Firefox, or IE.)(4 p).
3. Alena Friedrich (Author), 2001, Typical English Food. Effects of History and Tradition, Munich, GRIN Verlag, <https://www.grin.com/document/14479>
4. Nematovna, Ostonova Sanam, and Xikmatova Makhfuza Xikmatovna. "English language in a historical perspective and forming of vocabulary." *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal* 10.5 (2020): 1488-1492.es. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal* Year : 2020, Volume : 10, Issue : 5 First page : (1488) Last page : (1492) Online ISSN : 2249-7137. Article DOI : 10.5958/2249-7137.2020.00483.8
5. Ostonova Sanam Nematovna, *World Bulletin of Social Sciences (WBSS)*

Available Online at: <https://www.scholarexpress.net> Vol. 3, October- 2021 ISSN: 2749-361X 49
Traditional Complication Major Translation in National Cultur.

6. Sadullaeva Matluba Akhrorovna Publication date 2020/10 Journal EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD) Volume5 Issue 10 Pages 231-235 Publisher EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD)SJIF Impact Factor: 7.001| ISI I.F.Value:1.241| Journal DOI: 10.3671Authors

7. Matluba Sadullaeva Akhrorovna Publication date 2020/11 Journal International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) Volume 4 Issue 11 Pages 51-54 Publisher International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) ISSN: 2643-91233

8. Остонова, С. Н. National traditions and rituals in modern Uzbekistan (basing on the analysis of Uzbek traditional meal «Palov») /

9. С. Н. Остонова. — Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. 2020.-№47 (337).С. 199-203. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/337/75335/> (дата обращения: 28.10.2021

10. Остонова, С. Н. National traditions and rituals in modern Uzbekistan (basing on the analysis of Uzbek traditional meal «Palov»)/С. Н. Остонова. Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый.-2020.-№ 47(337). 199-203.стр -URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/337/75335/> (дата обращени 28.10.2021).

11. ОстоноваС.Н.Духовности Гуманизм Человека в ЭпохуВозраждения./ Revival.P Вестник науки и образования 2020. № 8 (86). Часть 1.

12. Молодой ученый Ostonova S. N.Uzbek clothes through the prism of the national customs and traditions of the ethnosat the XIX-XX centuries..162

13. Alena Friederich (Author)Typical English Food. Effects of History and Tradition Term Paper (Advanced Seminar), 200122 Pages, Grade.

14. Ostonova Sanam Nematovna CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HISTORY VOLUME: 02 ISSUE: 09 | SEPTEMBER 2021(ISSN: 2660-6836) “Major Translation Traditions in Cultural Compilations.”

15. Ostonova Sanam Nematovna, “NATIONAL FOOD IN THE GREAT NATIONAL VALUES OF THE UK” TJE - Thematic journal of Education ISSN 2249-9822 Vol-7-Issue 2022 <http://thematicsjournals.in/index.php/tjedDOIhttps://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6051566> UIF 2020= 7.528 IFS 2020= 7.43

16. Остонова Санам Нематовна.“ВЕЛИКИЕ БРИТАНСКИЕ НАЦИОНАЛЬНАЯ ЕДА И ИХЦЕННОСТЬИ.” EURASIAN JOURNAL OF MATHEMATICAL THEORY AND COMPUTER SCIENCES Innovative Academy Research Support Center UIF = 8.3 | SJIF = 5.916 www.in-academy.uz Volume 2 Issue 4, April 2022 ISSN 2181-2861 Page 11.

17. Djalilova Z. O. Studies on gender linguistics in the field of Uzbek language //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 3.

18. Obidovna D. Z. &Sadullaev Denis. (2021). Formulas of speech etiquette in a gender-engineered communication strategy. central asian journal of theoretical & applied sciences, 2 (6), 5-11. Retrieved from<http://cajotas.centralasianstudies.org/index.php/CAJOTAS/article/view/180>.

19. Джалилова З. О., Хасанов К. А., Султонов А. А. Роль научного управления в процессе обучения высококвалифицированных врачей в новом Узбекистане // Молодой ученый. – 2021. – №. 26. – С. 377-379.

20. Obidovna D. Z. Comparative Analysis Of Uzbek Men's And Women's Speech Through The Prism Of Gender Linguistics // Central Asian journal of literature, philosophy and culture. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 22-26.

21. Obidovna D. Z. Gender issues in foreign theoretical linguistics: concerning the history of the issue // Gender issues. – 2021. – Т. 7. – №. 6.

22. Djalilova Z. O., Juraev S. S., Kosimov S. M. Latin as a professional language of medical workers // Международный научно-практический электронный журнал «Моя профессиональная карьера». Выпуск № 23 (том 1)(апрель, 2021). Дата выхода в свет: 30.04.2021. – 2021. – С. 79.

23. Jalilova Z. O. On the formation of the language of scientific literature in the history of the english language // E-Conference Globe. – 2021. – С. 18-22.

24. Obidovna, D. Z., & Sulaymonovich, D. S. (2022). THE CONCEPT OF "HEALTHY LIFESTYLE" IN PSYCHOLOGICAL RESEARCH. ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions, 3(06), 53-64.

25. Jalilova Z. O. Concerning the issue of terms, having a place with various morphological classes (in view of the example of the terminological arrangement of social action) // Новый день в медицине. – 2020. – №. 4. – С. 501-503.

25. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). Speech Behavior and its Gender Specificity on the Basis of the Main English Language Variants. Middle European Scientific Bulletin, 22, 199-205. Retrieved from <https://cejsr.academicjournal.io/index.php/journal/article/view/1146>

26. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). GENDER DIFFERENTIATION OF MASCULINE AND FEMININE VERBALIZATION. European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies, 2(05), 59-65.

27. Dzhililova, Z. O., & Mirfajziev, K. (2021). Latin as the language of medicine. Молодой ученый, (41), 35-37.

28. Dzhililova, Z. O. (2021). History of formation of Latin language. Молодой ученый, (41), 34-35.

29. Dzhililova, Z. O. (2021). The Latin language's international status. Молодой ученый, (41), 32-34.

30. Dzhililova, Z. O., Izomova, S. G., & Ahmedova, G. A. (2021). Intercultural communication and the Latin language. Молодой ученый, (24), 398-400.

31. Dzhililova, Z. O., Hajdarova, N. S., & Tashpulatova, N. A. (2021). Latin in the Contemporary World. Молодой ученый, (24), 400-402.

32. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). GENDER SPEECH BEHAVIOR IN THE CONTEXT OF THE SOCIO-LINGUISTIC FACTOR. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 3(6), 190-198.

33. Djalilova, Z. (2022). POLITENESS IN WOMEN'S DISCOURSE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. Academic research in modern science, 1(11), 29-34.